

Strategies and Tools of Social Media Marketing In the Luxury Fashion Industry

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Abstract

This study proposes a central concept such as social media marketing, in the luxury sector, must be able to keep up with the evolving technology, must perfect its offer for an increasingly demanding market and must seize digital opportunities and make the most of them. Several studies have highlighted the growing importance of digital in the high end, the need for companies to adopt an increasingly multi-channel approach and increasingly diversified by markets. The research question behind the developed work is to demonstrate that a strategy that considers the web is strongly necessary for luxury brands, but at the same time it does not need to look like a mass market strategy, resulting in inconsistency with the main features of luxury brands: exclusivity, uniqueness, rarity, superiority, singularity, prestige. Luxury fashion brands have to deal daily with the balance between safeguarding the exclusivity of the brand on the one hand, an increasing demand in the global market, intensification of distribution methods and the explosion of e-commerce, from the other side that seems to be in contrast with the set of meanings that revolves around luxury brands.

The objective of this work will, therefore, be to develop a more in-depth understanding of the strategies implemented by the brands operating in the fashion sector with regard to social media marketing and to analyse the effect it has had in businesses highlighting, such as social networks they also give opportunities in this area.

Keywords; *Digital marketing, luxury brand, luxury fashion, online communication, Social media marketing, social networks.*

Introduction

The digital revolution and the birth of Web 2.0, as well as new consumption habits, have radically changed the current society and this has affected the marketing and communication strategies at the managerial level. In recent years the luxury industry has been strongly influenced by the rapid evolution of digital technology, technology, and the Internet. The use of the internet and new technologies have contributed to the growth of the market and its various sectors, with an advantage for the luxury industry. It was a challenge to adapt to the new process, times have been slow given that this market has always adopted a strategy based on supply and not on demand, because luxury products attribute prestige status and stand out for their excellent quality, the high price, the highly exclusive and symbolic character. Instead, the principles of the Internet are democracy and accessibility that at first glance appear to be in contrast with the characteristics of luxury just exposed. Luxury consumers are highly digital, mobile, social and extremely demanding and are always looking for continuous information, news and dialogue with the brand; they love word of mouth and use different channels and tools to communicate and express their opinions. Through social media they have the opportunity to review and discuss products, events, and ideas on online forums, playing an increasingly influential role in shaping the public perception of luxury fashion brands.

The objective of the paper is to clarify the principles of management of luxury brands to become and remain so effectively, from the point of view of digital communication through the use of social media marketing tools. From the comparison between social media and luxury brands, these seem to be incompatible but looking more closely at the tools made available by the web 2.0. they have different aspects that luxury brands can use to their advantage to promote online exclusivity. New technologies are increasingly important among individuals who connect via social networks and mobile. The sociological, economic and marketing literature in recent years has dealt with the study of luxury and social media in greater detail, as this market continues to grow, despite the economic crisis. This work aims to give a complete vision of the new era of Web 2.0 by analysing in a rather broad and literary way, the various innovations that compose it: features, communication tools and the role of users. In particular, we focused on social media marketing and on the relevance of social networks. Then we focused on social media marketing strategies in the luxury fashion sector, with particular attention to content, the customer experience, the creation of dreams and value. After discussing the strategies and explaining why social media can be an opportunity for luxury

brands, the aspect of tools such as storytelling, blogger influencers, mobile applications and e-commerce on the website have been deepened. The need to create valuable content to reinforce brand awareness and to trigger a high level of user engagement was highlighted. The work ends with an analysis of a study carried out in the context of luxury fashion strategies.

1.The social media marketing strategies of luxury brands

The first approaches to change in both digital communication and the luxury market date back to 2005 until the radical change from 2012. This type of communication for the brand, for the consumer, for the designer, and for the brand has potential, the digital has gone from "cheap to chic in a click" and in addition to being useful for turnover it is also for the positioning of the product. With the technology you can communicate luxury products while remaining consistent with the company's positioning and communication style, you will have to analyse and develop right touchpoints (points of contact between brand and customer) during communication periods and companies will have to a constantly developing market, transforming the way and communication models of a world with precise rules in order to better respond to change.

To set up an effective SMM (social media marketing) strategy, first of all, we need to analyse the initial situation of the brand and define the objectives, then it is necessary to study, plan and develop the campaign and identify the most suitable social media mix. The contents are fundamental for which the next step is to study and create content to be distributed on social media. Once distributed manually, there is the monitoring phase of the latter, the analysis of the results and eventually any updates. As mentioned, digital is useful for positioning and strategies to keep it high without increasing the brand. They have been identified by Logotel, company that accompanies the transformation of companies, in particular, has identified the key points on which to build the digital strategy of the luxury brand. These points are the technology that should be considered a means and not an end, the contents and the customer experience. For content, the concentration falls on the pluses offered by the brand thanks to exclusivity, such as brands that enhance the values narrating stories related to contemporary art including cinema, fashion, music, design by studying the interests and preferences of potential and current consumers. Or brands that have chosen to work on specific projects to enhance their values such as Tiffany, who created whatmakeslovetrue.com, a digital space dedicated to the original approach to love, where couples are recommended, marked by more romantic places New York and collected themed spots designed by the consumers themselves. As for the customer experience, to strengthen the value of the brand, this must learn to produce emotions by "living the product" through for example exclusive communities, for advice and services for the consumer, or as a place of comparison for consumers. To create positioning, the fundamental elements are what is communicated and where it is communicated. In fact, the main difficulty was always that of transmitting in the correct way, the fundamental points of the strategy and the guidelines of luxury products. Unlike mass communication that has the usual function of selling, luxury has different and precise rules to create the dream and recharge the value of the brand on any platform, to engage the consumer and keep their own positioning. The exclusivity, as a distinctive feature of these products, is transmitted with top-down communication, combining the ability to generate wishes and expectations in the consumer and visual languages favouring social media and fashion blogging. The communication of the luxury brand is very far upstream from the purchase, speaks of the product and the universe of the brand in a dreamlike way and must be quite vague so that many people can identify and find their own part of the dream. This implies a refined and artistic communication, highly codified (luxury creates social codes) without being too dated, never direct, highly allusive. At this point it is clear how the luxury fashion sector is focused on the construction and narration of the image of the online brand, in the story of the complete and complex history of the brand, to increase its brand awareness. To achieve this, there are three main trends:

- a "mythological" construction of the brand that finds its roots in the history of the brand, its founders, designers or places of origin and this element emerges both in the descriptions of the information on the social channels and in the creation of dedicated initiatives;
- a narration linked to the lifestyle, that is the story of products, events and initiatives through the delineation of a lifestyle inspired by the brand by inserting the products in everyday life and creating a real universe, as for example Burberry presents a very broad on social media centered on its distinctive trait (being English) telling the brand with this type of narration;

- a narration focused on products, which remain the central element for the construction of the online strategy, such as the extensive use of links to catalogs and online shops, but are also the way to tell the brand and its philosophy.

These trends are styles that can be alternated for the same brand during the year depending on the period or the communication strategies and the positioning, advertising crowding, contents, themes and targets with which to interact are opportunities that these can seize., while the limits are represented by excess followers, by the search for non-performing contacts and by accesses or registrations not aligned to the target. The positioning rules and the guidelines are different for each brand, but it is possible to aggregate them and the values to consider that come out are four:

- Uniqueness: being the unique product, each format channel or vehicle must meet the same criteria of uniqueness;
- Impact: the emotional, visual and sensory one is "the first moment of truth" and must always be taken care of;
- Quality: passing the product directly to the media and digital communication vehicles;
- Position: the general concepts of media planning, pre- and post-analysis of frequency, coverage, and crowding become values for the selection of formats and vehicles channels.

For the communication of luxury on digital channels, the models to identify the target are different and assume great importance, the target reacts directly to the solicitation of communication of some products, namely people who cannot afford it and this does not lead to a correct evaluation of redemption and of the call to action of the message.

After the product and the target, the content is another fundamental variable to realize a correct marketing strategy for luxury products and must be divided into two sub-variables:

- the content of the product (the one produced by the brand and used on its own channels), essential to correctly integrate the communication making it unique on all media;
- the communication content (the integral part of the channel where the brand message will appear), to be analysed in depth to select the communication channels.

The problem of the internet is the truthfulness and quality of the information on the web as content can be produced by copywriters, aspiring journalists, passionaries, visionaries, but also authors completely unprepared on the subject. Luxury brands think about the type of content: some on the one related to storytelling of heritage, others on the emotional and value, and others to the consistency of content and for this, you need fashion bible, lifestyle editor and influencer platform. For a message related to the product or to an initiative, in particular, the consistency, it must be relevant above all for the personalized content, destined to the recipient also in a way disconnected from the context, in this type of content we must purchase specific audience to customize the message conveyed. The best way to do this is to bind the data selling platform to its CRM database and recognize its most strategic customer profiles in inventory. It is, therefore, necessary to segment its customers and integrate the algorithms of the programmatic purchasing platforms. A strategy of social media marketing that in the luxury fashion sector is able to get results to the brand is the use of video: they give the possibility to know the history of the product and that of the brand, they are able to lead the emotions and the high evocative value. Among the digital media, for a luxury brand, the video is the most relevant component, it is a format rich in content that must be created on the basis of the platform on which it will be conveyed to increase social networks, the website, and other plans editorials. With digital social videos, being of great impact, stories can be told enhancing the subject, that is the brand and the message to communicate as Cartier did during the Valentine's Day through the project "The Proposal" supported by an important campaign of communication in several countries, posted from the beginning on Facebook to support the campaign dedicated to the day of the engaged, then on other channels both paid and owners. The project is developed on three different videos: "at the museum," "in the elevator" and at the airport," as if to explain that the right moment for the "proposal" can be present everywhere and that a Cartier ring is the right way to contextualize it. Stories are unique and different with structured storytelling and a common ending to all three. The timing of the campaign was also strategic as it was left on the most romantic days of the year and was also useful for the launch season for the wedding season. These videos are emotional, contextualized in moments of common life and studied in detail so that a luxury brand must do for an important digital production conceived on a worldwide scale. The videos transmitted brought the user to the official website of the Maison, directly to the page dedicated to the project, where the

future Cartier customer can inquire about the art of jewellery, know the details of the chosen jewel and of course buy it directly online. The narrative was used to add an emotional context around the product and the stories told were intended to influence consumers in the decision on Cartier for romantic moments embracing the dream of women of all time. The sites are different, and the luxury fashion industry has rules established in relation to the type of channel selected that defines whether the content is suitable or not to the context in which it is positioned, it is difficult to understand which spaces are correct, which are performing and which are effective for the premises of the communication plan and in fact basic training and experience is required. Luxury is attentive to the product and the type of processing of every moment of communication, and for this sector, it is crucial to define the content of a site, the editorial quality, the quality of individual articles and therefore by definition, the target to which you are going to communicate. It is the content that rewards and leads the planning choices. We must give the right weight, and the right relevance to the publisher, the journalist, the heritage and the authority of the brand, the site's quality engine, this value must never be sacrificed for the benefit of non-qualitative numbers and views. The integration of the communication project into the correct content is vital to continue to communicate and strengthen its brand identity. The pure digital players know how to offer the consumer experiences and services related to the usability of e-commerce and the most captivating and memorable contents of the individual brands. In the physical store, luxury brands are introducing digital innovations to innovate the experience so that it is more revealing for an increasingly digital savvy target and to gather significant information on individual customers to build a personalized service. This digital transformation allows to recognize customers, facilitate the use of multimedia content, bring in the boutique the most social aspect of shopping or allow strategic processing on the conversion capacity of a specific showcase or a specific collection. Innovations that must be integrated with other communication channels so that they are strategic such as for example the website, e-commerce or mobile social activities. To develop an integrated digital campaign aligned to the brand and the opportunities of the new platforms, there is not an ideal strategic model for all players in the sector but we must take into account the marketing objectives identified by geographical area and understand the opportunities of the new platforms of programmatic buying (opportunities to reduce the dispersion of the reached audience and to personalize the message while safeguarding the context in which the message is delivered) in these areas. One of the strategies can be to introduce the digital world of the brand in reality, as for example, Burberry did in 2012 with Burberry World Live: a boutique with 100 screens, 500 speakers and the world's highest retail indoor screen; realizes this integration with a series of live events and free concerts that have told the brand throughout the year with the aim of creating a unique and emotional experience and at the same time, to increase brand awareness in absolute terms. The London flagship store of this brand was designed with the aim of increasing customer engagement and in-store sales through a digital and tactile event, aimed at showing off the brand's cultural and social heritage. The simplicity to participate has contributed to the success of this strategy in fact this was possible through social platforms, especially in the official site there was a special section where customers were invited to become followers of the brand on Twitter to get real-time information on the tickets of the event and on the various operations in progress. Technological development is to the advantage of the fashion world, reaches millions of consumers at no cost and attracts customers to interact with brands, so the social media that have changed the way we live the daily life and the relationship with others, are unmissable today. Even the luxury brands, for this reason, have had to rethink the communication strategies that have to face online with new fans and their current customers as they are online on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram or other social media and comment both the products and the choices. Social media is used to gather information and decide on purchases, luxury brands exploit the characteristic of interactivity of social media to reach their target, ask for advice and listen to what they need, and they do it by participating in tweeting, blogging, and networking. Before the consumer could choose between a few brands, today it is no longer so everything is played on the stimuli so those who invest in the online and play in an integrated way and will appropriately stimulate word of mouth will be able to gain a competitive advantage over competitors. As we know, most brands were a bit 'reluctant to use technology and only recently it was understood that social media do not act against the positive reputation of the brand and can instead be an opportunity for communication. To increase the value of dreams and fame, luxury brands use sites, blogs and communities because they are excellent tools for this but the risk of causing damage to the brand is also considerable, especially for established brands as negative information on the web can spread at very high speed, so the brand must

monitor the web carefully so that the customer's dream is not destroyed. For example, to address this issue, Chanel implemented the strategy of opening up to bloggers. Fan communities are an important part of the discovery process for new initiates and a way to reassure existing customers that their passion is shared by others. Finally, we see that time is one of the obstacles of the Internet for luxury brands as it is the world of the flash, a world where time can, however, be managed by each of us and in fact brands can use movies that last long enough communicate part of their dream or a website that is an excellent opportunity to attract new potential customers and show them the dream in a real communication suited to luxury. The luxury brands began to use social media in 2009: Burberry launched a social network, "Artofthetrench.com, with the aim of arousing admiration for the design of the trenches and to have fans communicating its culture with the customers, after the launch of the site online sales have increased, and the participation of online customers has meant that the ideas for Burberry were expanded. Dolce & Gabbana uses social media in order to get direct feedback from its customers, invites fashion bloggers to their shows that instantly upload event feedback on Facebook and Twitter. Chanel, Louis Vuitton, Yves Saint Laurent, and Stella McCartney now have Facebook, as well as Twitter and Instagram accounts. To generate brand awareness, brands tend to rebuild vertical communication strategies on social media, share news on flagship products and collections, or publish content that covers all the values of the brand and in this sense Burberry has succeeded because it has been able to maximize the 'awareness offline, successfully mix marketing campaigns on different social media and has articulated its presence on the platforms in a very consistent way. All brand profiles on social media show high circularity between the platforms with the presence of many links that refer to the different profiles of the brand and with the dissemination and circulation of cross-platform content in photos and videos. This is accompanied by the tendency to direct the flow of navigation with links that are on posts or social profiles to online stores and websites, emphasizing the centrality of the product and online purchasing practices as a central goal for the most brand.

2.The tools of Social Media Marketing

Storytelling

For a digital strategy, the art of storytelling can be that factor able to create a relationship with the user so strong as to actively push it towards action. Storytelling is relevant if we talk about communication, relationships, and contents for luxury brands. This practice develops contents for communication that have symbolic depth, narrative value and ability to appeal to the public imagination: it is the art of building stories to establish a relationship, actively involve its audience and arouse emotions. The complex of contents that are created uses symbolic elements that are able to attract the interlocutor in order to provoke an involvement made of imagination and memory, which is why the use of images that involve a more detailed interpretation with respect to the content is frequent. textual and which are able to trigger greater associations. We emphasize the components of products that can move, to manipulate the irrational impulse to purchase, to persuade and engage in the consumer experience. In their marketing strategies, luxury companies "are not selling products, they are selling an image," Friedman said in an interview for The New York Times; they must communicate coherently with the complex value that the brand expresses. Storytellers integrate communication channels and use each content as a piece of their story. Communicating the story behind the product, illustrating the values that define a luxury brand, is essential for an effective marketing operation in the luxury sector, for example you can tell the story of your heritage on all product pages and digital content, explaining what the brand represents, whether it guarantees luxury, quality, performance or style. Credibility must be at the base of each story to convey trust and to do so we must tell with simplicity and clearly bring out the values always using their own style to be recognized by the user. A successful case was for example the advertising conceived as a film dedicated to Chanel n.5 in which the brand is always visible from when the actress sprays the perfume before leaving home until you see it printed on the surfboard by she used all this and wanted to show that the essence of Chanel faithfully accompanies the audience during every moment of the day and highlights the style of Chanel, a woman with many commitments but who puts love first.

Blogger Influencer

Today it is also necessary for luxury brands to be more engaging and to be drivers of conversations, creators of new projects and stories to convey the emotion of the experience and to do it in the best way. Luxury

brands adopting the strategy of "working together": create customized by influencers to give different interpretations of the garments created, deliver the social accounts to an influencer for a few days to create more original and impactful content, involving bloggers to increase the appeal between tutorials and user generated content, they drop influencers for the launch of new collections. Sharing on social networks, companies satisfy the desire to know and discover followers, and they respond with feedback. This is why influencers play an important role because they revolutionize the way of enjoying fashion and current trends, given that they are present both on blogs and on social networks with profiles, which they use to leave reviews on the news, to attract the attention of consumers. From the fusion of this activity and that of the brand those who love fashion will feel integrated into the news and events. Bloggers or influencers can play an important role in the communication strategy of a luxury brand such as Chanel who, relying on influencers for its campaigns, have exploited their personal social channels in a natural and credible way; but it is not only fundamental the choice of ambassadors that must be in line with the values of the brand, it is also know how to use them: looking at Dior or Chanel you immediately think of celebrities of the highest level, but not all brands have such possibilities and especially the themselves. The role of bloggers is becoming increasingly important as a demonstration of this can be thought of how many bloggers and online influencers are invited more and more in the front row at the fashion shows. The appropriate influencers are an integral part of the brand's strategy as they act as message amplifiers and create a bond of trust between brand and consumer.

Application for smartphone and tablet

The focus on mobile is always greater, given its enormous diffusion and the applications briefly called "APP," must be part of an online marketing strategy and among the luxury brands are becoming more widespread. Today these tools, which can take the form of a diary, a story and a narrative, help to set up a more targeted communication strategy and the luxury fashion houses are increasingly aiming to seduce digital users in this way and to hit the online consumers in a new way. From the Admob mobile metrics report it emerges that iPhone users download an average of 8.8 free apps per month and buy at least one, and most of them have a strong connection with their device, from this we can already understand why many brands of luxury have taken the opportunity to create app rich in multimedia content, directly related to e-commerce or social media. The evolution of location services and mobile commerce, combined with the spread of smartphones, make it necessary for luxury brands to adopt a real strategy to penetrate significantly in this market, expanding their media mix and their marketing tools. They can have the structure of a minister; you can see highlights of the last show with photos, videos zooming on clothes and accessories and can contain news and a store locator. Chanel has even created one called Chanel Lovely Game which is a sort of slot machine for iPhone. Reinterpreting the casino game with a touch, you scroll, and if you are lucky, you can compose the latest creations of the brand with a lot of scoring. This allows you to play, interact and fully experience the lifestyle of the brand. Not only applications to keep in touch with customers who are passionate about the brand but also to make luxury younger: on iTunes, luxury brands have made podcasts, real TV that is updated regularly with video content. Speaking in a direct and more intimate way to the consumer brings a huge advantage to a luxury brand, especially if brand values are maintained in a disciplined way. The new platforms of Apple, iPhone, iPad and iPod Touch allow a dialogue that offers a high quality user experience to consumers, but it is important to know how to dialogue with the target audience because the challenge, as in every aspect of web 2.0, is before all about the contents.

E-commerce and website

Almost all websites are multi-language portals from which to access the national (or language) versions of the sites. In most cases, online stores and store locators for points of sale on the territory, emphasizing the centrality of the product and the possibility of direct purchase. Visual communication is preferred as language, photographs and variable presence of videos linked to backstage, fashion shows or adv campaigns (more often in sections or dedicated pages). Textual language is used for descriptive texts or is better enhanced in news and online brand-related magazines. Websites have low visibility social media on which there are brands, appear only as a minimal style in home or entrance page (in some cases the links to social media can be reached after passing the entrance page as for example for Dior). The online site can present various promotional and cultural initiatives of the brand as well as focus on the online store by directly

integrating the latter and the product catalog. The luxury fashion has become a big market in e-commerce, and for this reason, big brands have had to change the processes to engage the customer radically, they had to think about a customer experience on all the channels that still remained distinctive and engaging. For e-commerce channels and new immediate purchasing opportunities (for example mobile payment) in the luxury world, they have not changed the consumer's purchasing methods, and they have certainly not become the first sales channels, unlike the other industries where the e-commerce plafond is much higher. The barrier is represented by the quality of the experience and the safety on the quality of the product (color, size, fitting, etc.) since the desire for tangibility of the product prevails while the aspects that can push digital shopping are a physical experience that integrates with the concept of showrooming and the introduction of exclusive services and customization available mainly online. There are big brands that, recognizing the need to rely on e-commerce have abandoned their specificity and have preferred the customer and his requests, finding a compromise to the penalization that online sales can lead to luxury brands like Cartier that to feel in step with the times, has created an e-commerce section with the aim of selling its image and not its products. The aim remains to present itself as a renewed and original company and not to sell online. Many luxury brands are reluctant to e-commerce convinced that the characteristics of luxury brands are incompatible with this channel, that fashion should be lived, tested and understood and that being luxury, the hallmark of exclusivity should not have everyone access their products.

3.The choices of social media in luxury fashion

Luxury brands that choose social media for communication. they must maintain their own standing of superiority and at the same time must remain coherent with their own DNA, that is, they must adapt to the individual channels, the different languages and the "rules" of each one but at the same time they must maintain a uniform editorial line and create a posting plan for each social channel. The luxury fashion about the choice of channels in addition to the use of Facebook are oriented towards social media that primarily offer a visual experience where it is facilitated the sharing of content, which inspire the user and allow the latter to create only useful contents for the brand like Instagram, Twitter, Pinterest e Tumblr. To set a successful strategy on social media, the basic concepts are involvement and exclusivity, correct and personalized identification and a multisensory experience are necessary. For luxury goods, using multiple channels is an important choice because digital allows interaction with demand and can inform, can perform transactional and relational functions and despite the luxury, companies were initially not inclined to use the web, in the last instead, the opportunity offered by the digital channel was evident. This type of marketing allows the company to involve the consumer to transmit the values of a brand: it puts it at the center of the scene, becomes the protagonist and companies can develop engagement actions and exploit word of mouth. Most influencers are present on the different platforms, but based on the objectives of a media strategy, one must identify the benefits that each of them can bring to the project depending, for example, on whether to promote an event or sell a new product in e-commerce. Each has different structural factors such as the structure of the content so you have to see if the platform allows only text or even images and videos, the duration of the content that can always be clearly visible or can only be momentarily. The social media that are used more in this sector to increase visibility through the shares and therefore the involvement of followers are Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. For each social media, individual brands do not all behave the same way; there are those who have official profiles on the platforms with an icon or link on the home page of the sites and those who do not have this link. Instagram is the most used: according to an analysis Exane Bnp Paribas on the communication trends in 2016 of the biggest luxury brands, it turns out that Instagram is the most used by Chanel, Luis Vuitton, Dior, D & G, Gucci and Prada since it centers the image and is a great tool to show the brand and create a real storytelling of the brand and the associated values. For the purpose of engagement, Instagram is the most interesting and most used social network because it offers direct and immediate contact with the user and also because it is perceived as innovative, simple and emotional, adjectives that summarize well the Visual Marketing that lies at the basis of its success. This social influence the range of users between 18 and 35 years and is a high emotional impact because of the photos, is the platform that lends itself well to brands that are related to lifestyle and fashion. 96% of the fashion brands are on Instagram with a very accurate profile, and daily, with captivating photos and videos, they promote their image and products, as emerges from Blogmeter's research (Top Global Fashion Brands on Instagram). Facebook and Instagram give the possibility to share mobile-friendly contents: articles with

news, photographic reports, direct reports about fashion shows or presentation events of accessories or products. They also have functions that make it possible to transform visits into purchases, by linking the profile to the official website and to online stores or by creating campaigns to advertise the brand. These social networks are perfect for creating the storytelling of the brand and has a very young average audience that represents the future of the luxury sector. Instagram is central to the social media marketing strategy for luxury brands and this is also confirmed by the numbers of shares and post events such as Fashion Week in Paris, Moscow, and Milan where, according to Blogmeter, only during the Milan fashion shows luxury brand has published an average of 31 posts producing 10 million total interactions. Twitter is used in many ways but the preferred tool for online audience engagement is the space dedicated to events and fashion shows, and it is no coincidence that successful tweets are about the latter. It is mainly populated by young people who seek a confrontation with experts on issues of interest and updates in real time on what revolves around, is the world of opinions where a subject can get in touch with important personalities. It is very important during the events because if an influencer tweets at that time brings a high increase in followers and an increase in engagement. It is customary to let the followers participate through a live show that leads him to discover the moments before the show by publishing videos or photos that portray backstage moments. It is often used to give information without providing answers to people and ignoring the importance of storytelling. If you want to make your brand known to as many people as possible and focus on brand awareness, Facebook is the most suitable social network. On Facebook dominate, enticing videos and the public is very active with a high number of comments, likes, and shares. Brands that have successfully built a huge following are Louis Vuitton which boasts more than 19M likes on facebook, Gucci more than 15M.

4.An empirical study on social media marketing and luxury fashion

A study conducted by A.J. Kim, et al. (Do social media marketing activities enhance customer equity?) On a sample of consumers of luxury goods with high purchasing power, indicates that the marketing activity of a luxury brand, using social platforms entertains customers, offers a variety of free content and allows a personalized search for information. Brand activities on these social media platforms create user interaction by creating the word-of-mouth effect. In contrast to existing marketing activities that directly address the real value of products or services, SMM's activity of a luxury fashion brand focuses more on the hedonistic and empirical values that can be achieved by indirect brand experience. The study examines the effects of social media, the marketing activities of luxury brands in the fashion industry, the client's heritage, and purchase intent, which are perceived by consumers to be significantly effective and the results lead to these conclusions:

- the SMM activities of luxury fashion brands include five constructs: fun, interaction, trendiness, personalization and word of mouth, including distinctive values compared to the old style of marketing.
- the SMM activities perceived by the customers are influential to all the equity clients since these activities act positively towards all and are quite effective. As a means of integrated marketing, these activities improve the value of capital by providing a kind of novel to customers that traditional media marketing does not usually provide. Since the main purpose of marketing communication is to strengthen the relationship with the customer and the creation of purchase intentions, SMM's activities contribute as effective marketing to communication. Growing interest in luxury, fashion brands must provide the values of luxury for customers in every way possible and social media seem to be an adequate medium to attract luxury consumers right now.
- brand equity has a negative influence on this study because, in the sample customer equity measurement process, the future buying behavior towards a certain brand was picked up by general luxury customers whose customer life cycle and the measured brand value was not relatively high. Secondly, due to increased competition among luxury fashion brands, it has become more difficult to maintain customer loyalty to a specific brand.

The results of this study indicate the great difficulty in measuring the future behavior of customers as the competition is increasingly intense and there are a lot of alternatives for customers, so prosperity no longer seems promising but it remains important to manage customers as valuable assets. Brands with social networks can pursue strong strategies aimed at a specific target. The great news that digital communication

has brought to luxury is the measurement in real time (at the time when the action is performed, the result is analysed) and the phenomenon of big data (a lot of information to analyse, understand and manage). To evaluate the social progress of a brand, the indices used are:

- Social Visibility: indicates the volume of conversations generated by a brand among social networks;
- General Visibility: indicates the volume of conversations generated by a brand on blogs, forums & news;
- Net Sentiment: indicates the relationship between positive and negative impressions perceived online;
- Reach Growth: indicates the growth of fans and followers of a brand, compared to the previous month;
- Social Engagement & Content: evaluates the brand's ability to communicate or respond to its audience, and how effectively the content is addressed through the social network.

These indices, used in Fashion Luxury Social, by Brandwatch.com show a positive change in the value of everyone, and together they allow us to get an idea of the social strategy used by each brand. The Internet is the most measured means in absolute terms, but it is difficult to evaluate, in the correct way, the real value that is generated by digital communication because every value refers to a role, the objective and the type of communication that one wants to achieve. especially for luxury brands, for example, a communication campaign, it can stimulate the desire for a product in Italy that can be sold in a boutique in another part of the world. For this reason, the sector had to quickly understand the correct measurement for its product in relation to the audience through research and analysis for the average variables because, for other of these, each brand is a world apart. There are brands that develop strategies on multiple platforms (such as Dolce and Gabbana that oversees a large number of social networks and has created different profiles on 6 different social media or foreign blogs) and those who use a limited number but exploiting them intensively, publish content regularly and have very high response rates from users. One way to catalyse users' attention is to capitalize on the awareness gained over time, to present products specifically designed for web fans who show the brand's philosophy, engage in live streaming or live-tweeting of fashion shows. From the platform point of view, brands tend to adopt international strategies by opening up numerous English-language profiles aimed at all the markets in which the brand operates. A social media marketing strategy is essential especially for younger consumers, aged between 16 and 35, the so-called millennials, born precisely in the boom of communication technologies. We have said that in the social media the presence of links on the brand homepage is minimal and sometimes they are absent, but this is not a central factor for the determination of the engagement with the user, it happens that the brand involves starting from social media and direct to websites and online stores instead of pushing the user from the site to social media. The important aspect to be taken into consideration for each communicative practice is the target audience and the ability to communicate when products must be promoted, so more than the number of images and posts; we must focus on the quality of the content. If you compare the various brands there are those who aim to have more engagement on Twitter and Facebook and focus on the potential of the platforms by choosing the channels based on specific needs rather than just addressing their site, those that point to influencers famous, those that create different content depending on the channel chosen and those who are interested above all in the content that users generate. To make the imagination aroused in the reader, an effective storytelling must use the power of video and images where words do not arrive, and if you focus on explanatory media, able to tell even by themselves, no further explanation is necessary. In order to differentiate oneself from competitors, it is necessary to offer the user an added value. It is necessary to communicate exclusivity as a characteristic of a luxury brand, clearly and directly highlighting what can be given more than the others. Today, an SMM strategy for luxury fashion brands is essential for communicating its image to consumers, and these must engage in social media, to defend their prestige and exclusivity by creating interesting, shareable and in-tune content with their positioning in the market.

Conclusion

Social media marketing allows companies to converse with web 2.0 users. This communication is, as mentioned so far, "peer" and in summary with a social media marketing strategy you can gather suggestions from customers to understand how the image is perceived by consumers and analyse strengths and weaknesses of the brand on the market, increase the frequency of comments and positive feedback on the company and product, involve the followers that can be transformed into brand ambassadors. This makes the brand experience more engaging and increases the perception of the quality of the services offered; defending brand reputation by monitoring online discussions in real time and understanding errors in the

relationship with customers in the communication strategy, allowing a quick remedy for bad word of mouth; limit costs as social media can assist and support consumers with minimal effort; save on market research and get more honest and direct feedback; increase brand engagement through conversations in which values are transferred, and consumers are led to visit social channels more than once; increase brand awareness and keep consumer interest always active to create a relationship of trust that reiterates the purchase. Luxury brands cannot do without a social media marketing strategy but must, at the same time, remain consistent with the traits that distinguish them. The generation that has grown on the web and with virtual social networks expects brands to use social networks just like they do, on the same platforms, responding in real time, making interesting content and responding personally in real time to be well seen by all. In the fashion luxury industry, not all users can be potential consumers, in fact, a brand would not be luxury if it did not include the exclusive appearance of those who can really afford such a product. Kapferer remembers that "Luxury goods must be desirable by everyone but only consumed by a select few" and this means that through social media companies must create the dream for everyone, even for non-customers but they must not be accessible to everyone else they would lose their exclusivity. The most intelligent luxury brands have therefore understood the value of the conversation and have built strategies for diversifying social communication on multiple platforms (since each has different characteristics) depending on the relationship they have with the public, focusing on cross-border circulation. content platform and remaining consistent with the essence of the brand. Storytelling is the heart of the universe of luxury and fashion: writing its own story through the use of more social media and creating a mix of virtual and real experiences "builds an integrated communication. So a brand must communicate on the web to increase its dream value, increase brand awareness at low cost while maintaining a positive image. The conclusions we can draw from the use of the internet for online sales of luxury fashion brands are different. To sell a product creates a personal, affective relationship between the brand and the customer and this one-to-one relationship is vital in the universe of luxury goods. Luxury has a strong human dimension that is purely relational, the aspect of the advice of the sales staff is decisive in luxury, it is part of the brand, therefore the distribution must be carried out so that the customer can buy in peace and security and the staff, must make understand all the subtleties of a product, must share the quality, the spirit of the place, objects and time present in each object. One of the problems of luxury today is the Internet dilemma as a web strategy is essential for a luxury brand. The Internet is an effective communication, experiential and advertising tool, but the channel that presents problems is e-commerce for this "a luxury product must communicate via the Internet but should not be sold via the Internet." This may come as a surprise as most luxury brands have an e-commerce site. The Internet is essential for high positioning and to recreate the distance with brands that are not of real luxury. Communicating and selling are two different things. Recreating the experience of a real boutique online does not sell because e-commerce sites reduce the dream of the brand by providing too many unqualified people with too easy access to products, make the personal relationship disappear and deny the invitation to experience one to one and moreover internet by definition is an anonymous world. Web 2.0 is an opportunity for customers in terms of after-sales, the presentation of new products while maintaining the goal of regularly bringing the customer to the point of sale in order to safeguard the physical link with the brand. The Internet is a world that is not sufficiently experiential so much that the sophistication and a multi-sensorial component of luxury are completely lacking. While the internet is a transparent and explicit world luxury is implied for example the price of a luxury product on the web, where everything is public, it is not always indicated, and for many, the internet is above all a good way to buy more cheaply. price, the opposite of the approach to luxury. The Internet is a virtual universe, where it is easy to introduce falsehood, while a luxury strategy is for the real world that must make a dream come true. In order for a luxury product to succeed on the internet, two conditions must be met: correct and personalized identification and multi-sensory experience. Even word of mouth that is unleashed on the web can never be compared to any advertising campaign, and social networks are the best channel to communicate to many the possibilities of very few. Luxury brands that have not started to adapt to digital transformation, or those who continue to see it as a channel not suitable for this sector, will have to struggle in today's and future markets. While luxury must be something exclusive, reserved for a few, on the other hand, it requires social recognition to gain value and prestige.

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